

GEOTHERMAL ACTIVATION OF GEOTECHNICAL ELEMENTS USING THE MIXED-IN-PLACE TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Mixed-In-Place (MIP) is a deep mixing technology invented by Bauer in the 1990s to execute geotechnical works, e.g., to install retaining walls for construction pits.

With regards to geothermal activation, deep soil mixing is deemed an ideal execution method, due to the beneficial heat transfer from soil to the geothermal probes when fixed to the structural steel beams installed. This patented approach results in a more sustainable overall design, particularly using MIP technology, which can initially reduce carbon emissions by 30% or more compared to traditional alternatives.

The potential for temporary geotechnical elements to provide a permanent geothermal activation seems to be underexploited. In addition to private construction projects, geothermal heat can also be used for large-scale or public projects. Specifically, the approach of low temperature district heating and cooling technology may even widen the potential of geothermal energy. Geotechnical elements, which have been installed for a temporary structural use, can become an integral part of a district-wide system that uses only renewable energy, as well as using the ground as storage to balance the system.

Keywords: sustainability, product carbon footprint, soil mixing, Mixed-In-Place, geothermal activation

SUSTAINABILITY GOALS IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY

In addition to considering the way we live and use infrastructure or buildings, the construction industry has to also contribute actively to reaching sustainability goals. The United Nations has specified a basis to do so by determining the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their AGENDA 2030 on how to develop globally in a more sustainable way. The 17 sustainability goals include ecological aspects, economic and social aspects. Considering these goals may help to develop sustainable products in construction, scaled down to the level of districts, buildings, infrastructure. etc., and to the construction site level as well — some with particular relevance for geotechnical works, see Fig. 1.

Considering that each decision taken for a structure affects its sustainability, a cooperation-based partnership can also contribute by finding sustainable solutions and pursuing these together as a team. To construct buildings with a much smaller carbon footprint or to activate geothermal energy to significantly reduce energy consumption during the building's service life, the right partners have to work together. In this context, the cheapest service provider is not automatically the one who offers the most environmentally-friendly and most effective solution. Consequently, sustainable solutions must be considered in awarding systems, not just price.

Fig. 1: Overview on specific SDGs and postulated targets of the UN, with relevance for geotechnical works

POTENTIAL OF GEOTECHNICAL WORKS FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Geotechnical works belong to construction and hence play a role for sustainability in civil engineering. The unavoidable impact on the infrastructure and the neighbourhood of a construction site, and of course on the natural ground conditions, are self-evidently affecting the overall sustainability of geotechnical products and need to be controlled [Bauer, 2022]. Provided the contract and site preparation allow, striving for the lowest possible carbon footprint and other sustainability benchmarks to complete the works shall become a standard task for specialist contractors, while not compromising the successful performance of the works.

At first glance, when looking at the potential of geotechnical works for sustainability efforts, it might seem limited to the construction phase only. However, the full lifecycle of a building or structure comprises other phases, starting with the selection of the site and terminating with the dismantling and recycling of construction elements at the end of use. It seems therefore logical to look for options to make use of geotechnical structures during the service life of a building, and one of these options is their geothermal activation.

In both cases, for construction and the building's service life, future assessment systems should consider geotechnical products as an integral part of the holistic sustainability, which requires the aforementioned early contractor involvement.

THE MIXED-IN-PLACE TECHNOLOGY (MIP)

A typical Mixed-In-Place (MIP) wall may have a nominal thickness of 400 mm or 550 mm and is constructed using BAUER's technique of mixing the existing soils using triple continuous flight augers. The triple auger's string has a maximum length of 25 m and can drill and mix one panel at a time with the same dimensions of up to 23.5 m x 550 mm. To have a continuous wall, the panels are installed in a double pilgrim sequence.

Fig. 2: MIP elements construction with triple drilling auger: up and down movement during drilling process with contrary rotation of the drilling augers ensures homogeneity of soil-cement mix (left) and a typical construction pit supported by MIP walls (right, Bauer)

First, the primary panels are installed, before the secondary panel closes the gap between them. Afterwards, additional panels are installed in the overlap area between the secondary and primary panels, making sure that at the end every location at the wall is mixed at least twice. The triple augers penetrate the soil while injecting the grout slurry simultaneously. After reaching the end depth, the augers alter their sense of rotation to start the homogenization process of the soil along the whole depth of the panel. After a section of the wall is done and while it is still fresh, steel beams are installed, using a laser level to ensure that the beams are installed to the right elevation. Fig. 2 may give an impression of how MIP technology is applied in practice and shows its structural function as a temporary retaining wall (see also www.bauer.de).

SAVING TRANSPORT AND REDUCING CARBON FOOTPRINT IN EXECUTION

The equivalent carbon emission ($\text{CO}_{2\text{eq}}$), expressing the product carbon footprint (PCF) or the traffic volume as an indicator (e.g., for noise emission and air pollution), act as a quantifiable measure for product sustainability. The EFFC/DFI Carbon Calculator allows users to compare the PCF of geotechnical products, and even if only covers a part of the full life cycle of a building, the numbers represent a major share and are therefore essential to allow for a reliable Life Cycle Assessment [Schlegl, 2019, Del Rio Melo, 2020; Ibuk, 2020/2021].

Examples show that enormous savings in terms of sustainability can be gained by selecting adequate construction methods. Specific calculations clearly state the sustainability potential for soil mixing methods. A retaining wall executed with MIP technology compared to standard diaphragm wall technology can reduce the PCF by 30% or more. Similar calculations all show the same trend and reveal that the major carbon emissions are embodied in the construction materials, leading to the conclusion that the amount of reduction in PCF can be initially estimated by an evaluation of savings in material consumption, Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: $\text{CO}_{2\text{eq}}$ balances for the geotechnical works at QH Track, using the conforming solution (DW+JG = Diaphragm Wall and Jet Grout Plug) in contrast to the variation (MIP+LWS = Mixed In Place retaining wall and BAUER LWS silicate gel grout plug), both solution [Bauer, 2022]

Fig. 4: Comparison of traffic volume for the geotechnical works at QH Track using the conforming solution (DW+JG) in contrast to the variation (MIP+LWS) [Bauer, 2022]

It has also been proven that another major advantage of the MIP technology is to reduce transport to and from the construction site, which can also be numerically evaluated for their contribution to more sustainable products for geotechnical works. Basically, the resource-efficiency of MIP is related to mixing concrete-like material directly in the ground by using the soil in-situ as aggregate, and thereby sparing not only transports for the supply of concrete to the site but also sparing transports for disposal of excavated soil off site, see Fig. 4.

THE GEOTHERMAL ACTIVATION OF THE GROUND

The use of geothermal energy is not a new idea. However, the potential of temporary or permanent geotechnical elements for activation does not yet seem to be sufficiently exploited, and the increasing building redevelopment might benefit from this potential. In addition to private construction projects, geothermal heat can also be used for large projects such as the prestigious “The Circle” project at the Zurich Airport, an enormous building complex that used geothermal piles [Kaiser, 2018].

Specifically, the approach of low temperature district heating and cooling technology may even widen the potential of geothermal energy. For instance, geotechnical elements are considered an integral part of a district-wide operated system using only renewable energies, where the ground is also used as a storage facility to balance the system. However, while it seems obvious that an implementation of geothermal energy from geotechnical elements for building services needs to be considered at a very early planning stage of a new building, that is currently not always the case. Consequently, this early-stage sustainable consideration should become part of the conventional planning process.

With regards to geothermal activation, deep soil mixing is deemed an ideal execution method. Due to the beneficial intergranular contact from soil to the soil-cement mix, heat is transferred without any discontinuity into the geothermal activated element. Then the heat is conducted to the probes attached to the steel beams installed for structural needs. For a project in the city of Füssen, Germany, a residential building with 14 housing units and the construction of MIP retaining walls, a BAUER energy wall is successfully generating 5.5 kW of heat with only 1.0 kW of electricity, resulting in a performance factor above 4 kW, which is considered a good average value already.

Fig. 5: Typical application of geotechnical elements to activate geothermal energy for buildings in winter and summer operation (left); a residential building in Füssen, Germany, under construction (right), where solar collectors will take over the task of heating the soil in the summer period as a variant

Fig. 5 shows the schematic function as well as pictures from the execution of this particular pilot project for which Bauer won the innovation award of the Bavarian construction industry association in 2019. Further projects in Lindau and Munich, Germany, have also been awarded including geothermal activation of a MIP wall. The key to making use of these temporary works for a permanent and sustainable purpose was the early involvement of the owner and the involved geotechnical specialist to consider the renewable energy supply concept by integrating the retaining wall and its surrounding soil as an energy accumulator and storage. Experiences from BAUER Energy Walls already executed, together with further projects of that kind under construction or in preparation, can reliably act as a reference for a general understanding of the necessary working steps for the specialist contractor.

Fig. 6 shows a layout plan of an excavation pit retained by an MIP wall. Vertical steel beams were installed as structural reinforcement for the MIP wall. A predefined number of steel beams were equipped with geothermal probes. This number was determined from an analytic study to investigate the energy concept for the building's service life. With this approach the temporary retaining wall becomes immanent part of the permanent building.

Fig. 6: Layout of a construction pit planned for the installation of a BAUER Energy Wall (left) and a detailing with either H or double-U beams with or without geothermal probes to be attached (right)

The basis for this energy concept is the ground's suitability for geothermal activation (in combination with the wall itself), which needs investigation in a very early planning phase, and to be discussed with the owner before a traditional energy concept has been finalized. Once the concept includes the geothermal activation of the ground, the necessary approval has to be applied for from local water authorities. Additionally, with regard to the long-term application of using the ground as a heating and cooling accumulator, Bauer has carried out an analysis to prove that the energy used for the building over its service life is effectively renewable, based on thermal response tests (TRT) and numerical simulations based on the TRT (Kaiser, 2013). The corresponding frequent regeneration of the ground and groundwater is a crucial part of the sustainability of the energy supply system. Hence, it is important that the ground is protected from a substantial temperature change, i.e., heating, in the long run. Consequently, the management system controls the wall and the surrounding ground, over a period of one year, to be frequently cooled down when heat is extracted during the cold-weather (winter) season, leading to a constant annual mean. To allow this repeated geothermal use in the winter season, heat must be fed back into the ground during the warm-weather (summer) season whereas the extracted lower temperature from the ground boosts the cooling system of the building, see Fig. 5. This overall balanced usage can be confirmed by numerical simulations calculating the adapted temperature of the circulating brine in the geothermal energy system over time, see Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: Balanced temperature curve of the system's brine over several years, from a numerical simulation (with FE)

The structural function of the retaining MIP wall system is generally governing the type and length of the vertical beams, also their spacing along the wall axis. The latter subsequently provides the number of potential adaptors to attach geothermal tubes. Depending on the energy design study, only a reduced number of steel beams is used. In the presented example in Fig. 6, it's every second beam. For peak loads, heat is directly generated with electricity.

The type of the steel beams also plays a role for planning and execution. The geothermal tubes are generally attached to the web of the steel beam next to the flanges. The leading-out position may vary dependent on the beam type. As the brine needs circulating through the tubes, they are laid out in loops over the length of the beam, while ending not less than 1 m below ground level, see Fig. 8.

For the aforementioned residential building, a basement floor was planned, which necessitated an excavation pit. An MIP wall was planned and executed to support the excavation, with steel beams as an integral part of the structural system to secure the excavation pit surrounding the whole plot. The geothermal probes were fixed to the steel beams prior to their installation into the still fresh MIP wall, as presented in Fig. 9 (left). The geothermal probes were fixed at the transition between the flange and the web of the steel H-beam. They were connected together at 0.5 from the bottom of the steel beam with a special connector, which was protected during installation with a steel plate. At the top of the H-beam, the leading-out connections of the geothermal probes were supposed to be above the ground level to be later fixed within the capping beam, Fig. 9 (right).

Fig. 8: Sectional view to the MIP wall with geothermal tubes with lead-out at a lower level below ground (left) and systematic illustration of leading-out connections between U-profiles or at the side of an H-beam (right)

Fig. 9: Lower end of one loop of geothermal probes attached to the steel beam ready for installation (left) and after installation with lose ends to be connected to the system (right, with a Bauer rig at work)

After the construction of the capping beam and subsequently the building itself, the geothermal probes were then to be connected to the heat pump in the basement. The cool-heat cycle can then come into operation.

To complete a system or make it more redundant, the energy wall can be combined with solar panels to add another renewable energy source to the house system, as practiced in Füssen. Also, the base slab can be geothermally activated and integrated into the system, as shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Preparation of geothermal activation of the base slab to add to the building's energy management system, left; with geothermal tubes lead out from the MIP wall at a lower level below ground (refer to Fig. 8), as per CAD layout plan (right, w/ ground anchors to tie back the temporary retaining wall visible)

Those probes were then connected to a waterproof system for basefloors and walls, on which a distributor is placed (Kaiser, 2016). The distributor is connected to a ground heat pump installed in the service basement compartment. As per Fig. 5 (left), the system was then connected to the solar panels fixed on the roof of the building to close the cool-heat circuit.

Fig. 11: BAUER Tight® pass through system with connection box [Bauer Resources],

CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Construction activities will continue to have an impact on the natural environment. It is, however, up to all stakeholders: the owner, the designer and the contractors, to determine how serious the impact of this initial share of a building's lifecycle will be. The special foundations industry with its geotechnical works can significantly contribute to a more sustainable, "green construction." A cooperation based on partnership is essential to mutually develop the best sustainable solutions, with as few boundaries as possible to allow the specialist contractor to bring in innovative solutions in the first place.

Geotechnical products should serve sustainability goals in the construction phase and can also become an integral part of a sustainability concept over the complete service life of a building. Such a sustainable solution may be the utilisation of geothermal energy through deep foundations or retaining walls. The soil mixing technology is deemed applicable and ideal here. Beside reducing the carbon footprint, less traffic reduces noise emissions and air pollution in the local environment, and directly contributes to social sustainability goals. In particular, the MIP technology can complete its general preference for sustainable geotechnical works, additionally, by its direct interlocking with the surrounding ground generating beneficial heat transfer properties. By this, traditional temporary works become permanent within the building's utilities management system, as proven in exemplary projects.

However, the necessary integration of the BAUER Energy Wall in the building services engineering program makes it necessary to start planning at a very early stage. Projects have been executed where foundation piles or retaining walls have been applied with geothermal tubes to use the geotechnical elements as accumulators. The general idea starts with the owner and considers the local authority's requirement to use renewable energy within a sustainable "heat and cool circuit." Once the feasibility of geothermal energy is confirmed, an overall concept can be worked out for the cool-heat circuit to serve the building. It has been proven that utilization of the geothermal storage of the MIP elements and their surrounding soil can be an essential part of such sustainable concepts.

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